

SPOUSAL COMMITMENTS AND STUDENT LIFE: A STUDY ON MARRIED STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Spousal Commitments and Student Life: A Study on Married Students in Higher Education

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Abstract

Balancing student life requires a commitment to academics while participating in social, athletic, and cultural activities, with parental guidance crucial in emphasizing the importance of academic goals. This balance becomes particularly challenging for married students, who must carefully manage the dual demands of marital responsibilities and academic obligations, necessitating strategic planning and robust support systems. The study focuses on the existing empirical gap by exploring the unique challenges and experiences of married students returning to academia while balancing family obligations. The study utilized a descriptive exploratory design and criterion sampling to investigate the unique experiences of five married college students balancing academic and marital responsibilities. The study employed an in-depth semi-structured interview utilizing a researcher-made questionnaire validated by experts. The study explores married students' challenges and strategies to balance academic and marital responsibilities, emphasizing the importance of time management, positive attitude, and personal attributes. The result highlights how effective communication and mutual support are vital in mitigating relationship struggles and maintaining harmony. The findings call for tailored support systems to promote married students' well-being and academic success, fostering a balanced and enriching experience in their academic and family lives.

Keywords: *married life, student life, married students, academic pursuit, married college student*

Introduction

Balancing student life involves dedicating sufficient effort to academic work while also engaging in the social (Mishra, 2020), athletic (Mannino et al., 2019), and cultural (Yolak et al., 2019) aspects of being a student (Beatson et al., 2021). Parental guidance is crucial in this balance, offering support, encouragement, direction, and love (Tus, 2021). College-educated parents, in particular, recognize the long-term benefits of higher education and convey the importance of obtaining a degree to their children, fostering an environment where academic goals are highly valued (Tutor et al., 2021). This support can significantly influence a student's ability to achieve academic success, a dynamic especially relevant for married students returning to academia to pursue their degrees.

Married individuals must navigate the complexities of marital responsibilities alongside academic demands, striving to balance personal and educational ambitions (Karunai & Rahaju, 2019). Pursuing higher education demands a careful balance between academic responsibilities and personal life, a more complex task for married students (Freedman, 2019). These students must meticulously plan their schedules to balance competing priorities effectively (Kordzanganeh et al., 2021). The challenge of achieving a balanced student life takes on a unique dimension for married individuals as they strive to fulfill both academic and familial obligations.

More research is needed on how spousal commitments impact student experiences. Given the demanding nature of higher education for married students, this is an essential area for investigation. College life is not just about academics; a fulfilling experience involves engaging in social activities, athletics, and cultural events, fostering a well-rounded student (Beatson et al., 2021). However, married students face an amplified balancing act. Their academic pursuits intertwine with marital responsibilities, demanding meticulous planning and prioritization to navigate these competing demands effectively (Karunai & Rahaju, 2019; Kordzanganeh et al., 2021). While parental support is recognized as crucial for academic success, particularly for returning students (Tus, 2021; Tutor et al., 2021), the unique challenges faced by married students in balancing academic and spousal obligations necessitate a deeper exploration of the dynamics involved.

In the study, the researchers explore the experiences of married students as they balance higher education and family obligations, utilizing Work-Family Conflict and Enrichment Theory (Greenhaus & Powell, 2006) alongside Family Systems Theory (Bowen, 2012). These frameworks allow the researchers to analyze the conflicts and synergies between academic and familial roles, shedding light on challenges while recognizing how successes in one area can enhance the other. The study examines family dynamics, coping mechanisms, and support systems.

Despite existing research on student life balance and parental support, there is a significant empirical gap in understanding the unique challenges faced by married students who return to academia. The study addresses the empirical gap by exploring the experiences of married students balancing higher education with family obligations. The study highlights distinctive challenges, such as time pressures and role incompatibilities, while recognizing how successes in one domain can positively influence another. Moreover, this research aims to address this gap, providing insights into how married students can achieve balance, thereby enhancing their academic success and overall well-being.

This research seeks to uncover a deeper understanding of how married students balance academic demands and spousal responsibilities by investigating their coping mechanisms. By examining the intricate relationship between educational demands and family

responsibilities, the study aims to uncover effective mechanisms for managing domestic duties and the emotional aspects of marriage alongside academic workloads. These findings will provide valuable insights into the support systems and interventions that can enhance married students' well-being and academic success, ultimately contributing to the development of more supportive and accommodating environments within higher education institutions.

Research Questions

Balancing of student life with academic responsibilities is a well-documented challenge for many individuals pursuing higher education. However, for married students, the complexity of this balance intensifies as they navigate the dual demands of their academic pursuits and marital responsibilities. The intricate interplay between these two significant aspects of their lives requires meticulous time. The study specifically addresses the following questions:

1. How do the married students balance their academic and married life?
2. What are the struggles that married students face in pursuit of their degree?
3. What are the coping strategies of the married students when they face challenges in their academic and married life?

Literature Review

Spousal Commitments

Spousal commitments encompass a range of responsibilities and expectations between married partners. These commitments can be categorized into emotional support, household responsibilities, and financial obligations. Emotional support involves empathy, understanding, and encouragement, essential for marital satisfaction and stability (Mannino et al., 2019). Household responsibilities include managing daily tasks such as cooking, cleaning, and childcare, ensuring the smooth functioning of the household (Clark, 2019; Thorpe & Kuperberg, 2021). Financial obligations involve managing the economic aspects of the family, including budgeting, saving, and spending, which are crucial for financial stability and reducing marital conflicts (Kordzanganeh et al., 2021).

The nature of spousal commitments can vary significantly based on factors such as the relationship stage, cultural background, and the presence of children. In the early stages of marriage, couples often focus more on building emotional intimacy and establishing shared household responsibilities (Thorpe & Kuperberg, 2021). Cultural background influences how these commitments are perceived and managed; for example, some cultures may emphasize traditional gender roles, affecting the distribution of household tasks (Augustine et al., 2018; Freedman, 2019). The presence of children adds another layer of responsibility, requiring couples to balance parenting duties with their existing commitments, which can intensify the need for effective time management and support (Rindfuss & VandenHeuvel, 2019; Karunai & Rahaju, 2019).

As relationships evolve, so do the commitments. In long-term marriages, partners may develop more efficient ways to share responsibilities but also face new challenges, such as caring for aging parents or dealing with health issues (Beatson et al., 2021; Finkel, 2019). Cultural variations also influence how spousal commitments are adapted over time, with some cultures emphasizing family cohesion and mutual support (Thorpe & Kuperberg, 2021). Additionally, the arrival of children often necessitates renegotiating roles and responsibilities to ensure that both partners can fulfill their duties effectively while maintaining their personal and professional lives (Augustine et al., 2018; Rindfuss & VandenHeuvel, 2019).

Student Life in Higher Education

A unique set of demands and challenges characterizes student life in higher education. Academic workload is one of the most significant pressures, requiring students to manage multiple assignments, projects, and examinations (Mishra, 2020; Beatson et al., 2021). This workload often demands high time management and organizational skills to ensure academic success (Zuhara et al., 2017). Additionally, maintaining a social life is crucial for students' mental health and well-being, as it provides opportunities for relaxation, networking, and support. Balancing these social interactions with academic commitments can be challenging, particularly for students who are also managing family responsibilities (Horne et al., 2018; Mannino et al., 2019; Yolak et al., 2019).

Financial pressures add another layer of complexity to student life. Many students struggle with tuition fees, living expenses, and the need for part-time employment to support their education (Horne et al., 2018; Kordzanganeh et al., 2021). This financial strain can detract from their focus on academic work and increase stress levels, potentially impacting their overall academic performance. For married students, these financial pressures are often compounded by the need to support a family, making effective financial management critical to maintaining academic and family stability (Zuhara et al., 2017; Pepin et al., 2018; Clark, 2019; Kordzanganeh et al., 2021).

Moreover, the dual roles that married students play further intensify these challenges. They must navigate the complexities of marital responsibilities alongside academic demands, striving to balance personal and educational ambitions (Augustine et al., 2018; Karunai & Rahaju, 2019). This balancing act requires meticulous planning and prioritization to manage competing priorities effectively (Freedman, 2019). Married students often face unique stressors, including managing household tasks, providing emotional support to their partners, and fulfilling academic requirements, all of which demand significant time and energy (Zuhara et al., 2017; Alvarez

Sainz et al., 2019; Beatson et al., 2021).

Potential Impact of Spousal Commitments on Student Life

The interplay between spousal commitments and student life can significantly influence various aspects of a married student's academic journey. Positive impacts include increased motivation and emotional support from a spouse, which can enhance academic performance and provide a stable foundation for managing the stresses of higher education (Freedman, 2019; Finkel, 2019). A supportive spouse can help mitigate academic pressures by sharing household responsibilities and offering encouragement, leading to improved focus and productivity in academic tasks. These dynamic fosters a balanced approach where academic and marital roles complement each other, promoting overall well-being (Augustine et al., 2018; Clark, 2019; Finkel, 2019; Mannino et al., 2019).

Conversely, the additional responsibilities associated with spousal commitments can create time constraints and increase stress levels, potentially hindering academic success (Zuhara et al., 2017; Alvarez Sainz et al., 2019). Married students often experience significant stress due to competing demands on their time, leading to potential conflicts between their roles as students and spouses (Pepin et al., 2018; Freedman, 2019). This stress can result in sleep deprivation and reduced cognitive function, further impacting academic performance and family dynamics (Pepin et al., 2018; Karunai & Rahaju, 2019; Thorpe & Kuperberg, 2021). The challenge of balancing these dual roles necessitates effective time management and support strategies to avoid role overload and burnout (Alvarez Sainz et al., 2019).

Factors such as the relationship stage, cultural background, and presence of children can further influence how spousal commitments impact student life. In the early stages of marriage, couples may still adjust to their roles, which can heighten the stress of balancing academic and marital responsibilities (Thorpe & Kuperberg, 2021; Beatson et al., 2021). Cultural expectations can also affect how these commitments are managed, with some cultures placing more emphasis on family obligations, potentially increasing the burden on married students (Freedman, 2019; Finkel, 2019). The presence of children introduces additional caregiving responsibilities, making it even more challenging to allocate time and energy between academic and family roles. Addressing these challenges requires a holistic approach that considers the interconnected nature of academic and familial responsibilities and fosters resilience and mutual support within the family unit to enhance overall well-being and success (Augustine et al., 2018; Clark, 2019; Freedman, 2019; Rindfuss & VandenHeuvel, 2019).

Spousal commitments, encompassing emotional support, household responsibilities, and financial obligations, are crucial for marital satisfaction and stability. These commitments evolve based on relationship stage, cultural background, and the presence of children, requiring couples to balance various duties effectively. In the context of student life in higher education, the challenges intensify as married students must juggle academic workloads, financial pressures, and family responsibilities. This dual role necessitates meticulous planning and prioritization to manage competing demands. The interplay between spousal commitments and student life significantly influences academic performance and well-being. Positive spousal support can enhance motivation and academic success, while the added responsibilities can increase stress and time constraints, potentially hindering academic achievements. Factors such as relationship stage, cultural expectations, and childcare further affect this balance, highlighting the need for a holistic approach to effectively manage academic and familial responsibilities. This synthesis underscores the dynamic and interdependent nature of spousal commitments and student life, emphasizing their impact on married students' overall success and well-being.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive exploratory design (Cresswell & Cresswell, 2017) to delve into the unique experiences and challenges married students face in academia as they balance marital responsibilities with academic pursuits. An exploratory design using qualitative methods is chosen to gain deep insights into married students' personal and subjective experiences, capturing the complexities and nuances of their dual roles (Maxwell, 2008).

Participants

The study utilizes criterion sampling (Suri, 2011) to select participants, ensuring that specific conditions are met to address the research objectives effectively. The criteria for selecting participants are twofold: first, participants must be currently enrolled as college students; second, they must be legally married. By ensuring that all participants are college students and legally married, the study can accurately explore the unique challenges and experiences associated with balancing academic responsibilities and marital obligations. The approach strengthens the study's internal validity (Johnson, 1997) and helps generate findings that can inform targeted interventions and support mechanisms for married students in academia.

Table 1. Demographic profile of the respondents

<i>Respondent</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Years Married</i>	<i>Number of Children</i>
MS-1	29	Female	7	1
MS-2	28	Female	6	1
MS-3	26	Female	4	4
MS-4	25	Male	4	1

MS-5	25	Female	5	1
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The participants for the study consist of five (5) married college students enrolled during the school year 2023-2024. Among the participants are four (4) females and one (1) male, all of whom are legally married. On average, the participant's marriages lasted between four (4) to seven (7) years, and their ages ranged from twenty-five (25) to twenty-nine (29). Each participant has one (1) and four (4) children. The diverse group provides a comprehensive overview of the experiences of married students juggling academic and familial responsibilities within this specific age and marital duration range.

Instruments

The research instrument utilized in the study was a researcher-made questionnaire specifically designed to capture the unique experiences and challenges of married students in academia. The questionnaire was developed through an extensive literature review to cover various aspects of balancing marital responsibilities and academic pursuits. To ensure the instrument's validity and reliability, the questions were subjected to a rigorous validation process by three (3) experts in psychology and higher education. These experts reviewed the questionnaire for content accuracy, clarity, and relevance, providing valuable feedback incorporated into the final version (Asoodeh, 2022). The resulting questionnaire comprised open-ended questions, allowing for qualitative insights into the participants' lived experiences.

Procedure

The researchers conducted in-depth semi-structured interviews (Yin, 2014) with each of the five (5) participants. The researcher provided detailed information about the study to ensure informed consent was obtained. Interviews were scheduled at times convenient for each participant to minimize disruptions to their academic and personal lives and were conducted in private settings to facilitate open and honest discussion.

Guided by open-ended questions, the semi-structured interviews allowed for flexibility, enabling the researcher to delve deeper into topics as they emerged during the conversation. Each interview was recorded with the participant's permission and lasted an average of 27 minutes, sufficient to explore critical themes without causing undue fatigue. The interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim, with the researcher meticulously reviewing the transcripts to ensure accuracy and completeness (Kallio et al., 2016).

Data Analysis

The data analysis for this study employed thematic analysis to interpret the raw data from the interviews, following the six-step methodology proposed by Braun and Clarke (2017). The process began with the transcription of the recorded interviews. Each interview was meticulously transcribed verbatim, ensuring that every detail of the participants' responses was captured accurately. The step was crucial for familiarizing the researcher with the data and laying the foundation for the subsequent analysis.

Once the transcription was complete, the researchers immersed themselves in the data by thoroughly reading and re-reading the transcripts. This phase involved initial note-taking to identify preliminary patterns and potential themes. The next step was systematically coding the data, where meaningful text segments were labeled with codes that captured their essence. The iterative coding process allowed the researchers to refine and adjust codes as new insights emerged.

Following coding, the researcher collated the codes into potential themes, grouping related codes to form broader patterns. These themes were then reviewed and refined to ensure they accurately represented the data. During this phase, some themes were combined, others were divided into sub-themes, and some were discarded if they did not have sufficient supporting data.

After refining the themes, the researcher defined and named each one, providing clear definitions and identifying its essence. This step involved writing detailed theme descriptions and selecting illustrative quotes from the data to exemplify each theme. Finally, the researcher produced a comprehensive report, integrating the themes into a coherent narrative that addressed the research questions and highlighted the lived experiences of married students balancing academic and marital responsibilities (Kiger & Varpio, 2020).

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to strict ethical standards to ensure the protection and privacy of all participants. Transcripts were anonymized to safeguard participants' identities, and all recordings and transcripts were securely stored in encrypted files accessible only to the research team (Kamanzi & Romania, 2019). Participants were fully informed about the study's purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits and provided written consent before participating (Shaw, 2023). To enhance the credibility and trustworthiness of the data, preliminary findings were shared with participants for verification, ensuring that their experiences were accurately represented (Adler, 2022). Throughout the research process, confidentiality and data privacy principles were rigorously upheld, with all personal information treated with the utmost sensitivity and respect (Pietilä et al., 2020).

Results and Discussion

The findings from the study provide a comprehensive insight into the challenges and strategies married college students employ as they balance academic and marital responsibilities. Through thematic analysis of the in-depth interviews, several key themes emerged, highlighting the intricate dynamics of their dual roles.

Balancing Married and Academic Life

Figure 1 presents the overview of the thematic chart of the coping strategies of married students in pursuit of their degree. Four (4) significant themes were generated: time management and efficiency, attitude and mindset, personal attributes and characteristics, and prioritization and focus. Per themes, sub-themes were also generated and recorded.

Figure 1. Overview of the thematic chart on the how married students balance their married and academic life

Frame 1 displays the qualitative themes of the coping strategies of married students in managing their academic and married life. Moreover, Frame 1 presents sample verbatim responses in English or the language used (Cebuano) with a translation in English to support the themes and sub-themes.

Frame 1. Summary of the qualitative themes on how the married students balance their marrie and academic life

Theme	Sub-theme	Sample Statement
Time Management and Efficiency	Time Management	“Balance time with my family and my studies”
	Maximizing Time	“... kung pwede mabuhay sa school ginabuhay na nako” (If I can work on it at school, I do it there)
	Multi-tasking	“...while ga buhat ko atong mga buluhaton sa balay mag video call dayn ko sa akong pares” (...while I work on my tasks at home, I simultaneously video call my partner)
Attitude and Mindset	Optimism	“Thinking positive always”
	Acceptance	“Consequences of what I have done before”
Personal Attributes and Characteristics	Dedication and Motivation	“Dedication and motivation to pursue my degree”
	Discernment	“Prioritize my task accordingly to their importance and deadline”
	Pragmatic Outlook	“Setting achievable goals for both my academic and personal life”
	Balancing	“I don’t overload myself with too much work or expect too much for myself”
Prioritization and Focus		“dapat lang nako buhatong una ang importante dayun pag bigyan og tagad ang dapat pag bigyan og tagad” (I should prioritize first the important things then give attention to those that need it)

Time Management and Efficiency

The sub-theme of Time Management underscores the intricate balancing married students must perform as they navigate academic commitments alongside marital responsibilities (Freedman, 2019). The sub-theme reveals that these students often experience significant stress due to competing demands on their time, leading to potential conflicts between their roles as students and spouses (Zuhara et al., 2017). However, these individuals can also find enrichment through their dual roles, as effective time management strategies foster better communication and mutual support within the marital relationship. This strategy mitigates conflict and enhances their well-being and academic performance (Alvarez Sainz et al., 2019; Jephcott et al., 2023).

The sub-theme of Maximizing Time reflects married students' proactive strategies to optimize their daily schedules, ensuring that academic and marital obligations are met efficiently. These strategies are essential in reducing the stress associated with role overload and enhancing the quality of life in both domains (Horne et al., 2018). Maximizing time involves collaborative planning and prioritization within the family unit, where spouses work together to identify and implement time-saving techniques (Abreu-Afonso et al., 2022). This cooperative approach enhances individual productivity and strengthens the marital bond, leading to a more harmonious and supportive household environment (Rindfuss & VandenHeuvel, 2019; Shephard, 2019).

The theme of Multi-tasking highlights the necessity for married students to juggle multiple responsibilities simultaneously (Osuh & Ishola, 2021). While multi-tasking can lead to increased stress and potential burnout, it can also foster beneficial skills and competencies across academic and family domains. However, successful multi-tasking often requires a well-coordinated family system where individual roles and responsibilities are clearly defined and shared (Alkahtani et al., 2016). This cooperative dynamic can transform the challenge of multi-tasking into an opportunity for personal growth and mutual support, reinforcing the stability and functionality of the family system (Cambri, 2021; Zaiceva, 2023).

The overarching central theme of Time Management and Efficiency emerges as a critical factor in the lives of married students in academia. Effectively managing time and enhancing efficiency is pivotal in mitigating conflicts and enriching academic and marital domains (Beyramijam et al., 2020). Through strategic time management, cooperative planning, and adept multi-tasking, married students can navigate the complexities of their dual roles, leading to improved academic outcomes, stronger marital relationships, and enhanced overall well-being (Freedman, 2019). This integrated approach highlights the importance of viewing time management as an individual skill and a collaborative family process fostering resilience and mutual support (Pepin et al., 2018; Finkel, 2019).

Attitude and Mindset

The sub-theme of Optimism reveals how a positive outlook plays a crucial role in married students' experiences managing academic and marital responsibilities. Optimism helps buffer the stress of juggling these dual roles by fostering resilience and a proactive approach to overcoming challenges (Abbaspour et al., 2020). An optimistic attitude can positively influence the family dynamic, promoting supportive interactions and shared encouragement (Homaei & Dasht Bozorgi, 2018). This optimism helps students stay motivated and engaged in their studies and strengthens their marital relationship by enhancing mutual understanding and cooperation, thus enriching both spheres of life (Kazim & Rafique, 2021).

The sub-theme of Acceptance highlights married students' mature perspective when facing the inevitable trade-offs between academic pursuits and marital duties. Accepting the consequences of their choices reduces internal conflict and fosters a sense of control and accountability. Acceptance within the family system can lead to better communication and realistic expectations (Wallerstein, 2019). This acceptance enables students to navigate their dual roles more effectively, recognizing and mitigating the impact of their academic commitments on their marital relationship and vice versa, leading to a more balanced and harmonious life (Rindfuss & VandenHeuvel, 2019; Freedman, 2019).

The overarching central theme of Attitude and Mindset emerges as a vital element in the experiences of married students in academia. A positive attitude and a realistic mindset are essential for managing the interplay between academic and marital responsibilities (Freedman, 2019). Optimism fosters resilience and proactive problem-solving, while acceptance of consequences ensures realistic expectations and accountability (Homaei & Dasht Bozorgi, 2018). Together, these attitudes mitigate conflicts and enrich academic and family life by promoting mutual support, effective communication, and a balanced approach to dual roles (Abreu-Afonso et al., 2022). This integrated perspective highlights the importance of cultivating a constructive and adaptive mindset to thrive in the complex context of married student life (Finkel, 2019).

Personal Attributes and Characteristics

The sub-theme of Dedication and Motivation highlights married students' intrinsic drive to succeed in their academic pursuits while managing marital responsibilities. Dedication helps mitigate the stress associated with their dual roles by creating a sense of purpose and commitment that propels them through challenges (Arum et al., 2018). Motivation can inspire and positively influence the family unit, fostering a supportive environment where partners encourage each other's goals (Thorpe & Kuperberg, 2021). This dedication enhances academic performance and strengthens the marital bond by reinforcing a shared vision of success and mutual support (Freedman, 2019).

The sub-theme of Discernment underscores the critical ability of married students to make informed decisions regarding their time and

energy allocation between academic and marital responsibilities. Discernment helps identify priorities and make choices that minimize conflicts and maximize enrichment opportunities (Malone, 2018). Discernment within the family context leads to better communication and mutual understanding, ensuring that academic and marital needs are addressed thoughtfully. This capacity for discernment allows married students to navigate their complex roles more effectively, leading to more balanced and fulfilling lives (Beard, 2018).

The sub-theme of the Pragmatic Outlook reflects married students' realistic and practical approach to managing their dual roles. Pragmatism helps set attainable goals and maintain a healthy balance between academic and marital commitments. A pragmatic outlook fosters a cooperative family environment where expectations are aligned with realities, reducing potential conflicts (Clark, 2019). This practical approach enables married students to manage their responsibilities more efficiently, leading to sustainable academic and marital success (Regnerus, 2020).

The sub-theme of Balancing captures married students' ongoing effort to maintain equilibrium between their academic and marital lives. Effective balancing reduces role conflicts and enhances overall life satisfaction by allowing individuals to draw positive experiences from both domains (Sirgy & Lee, 2018). Balance within the family system leads to shared responsibilities and mutual support, creating a harmonious household (Nicklin et al., 2019). This continuous balancing act is essential for married students to thrive academically and personally, ensuring that both areas are addressed (Augustine et al., 2018).

The overarching central theme of Personal Attributes and Characteristics emerges as a pivotal aspect of the married students' academic experience. Personal attributes such as dedication, motivation, discernment, pragmatism, and balance are crucial for managing the dual demands of academic and marital responsibilities (Arum et al., 2018; Thorpe & Kuperberg, 2021). These characteristics mitigate conflicts and foster enrichment in both domains, enabling married students to achieve their academic goals while maintaining healthy and supportive marital relationships (Beard, 2018; Clark, 2019). This integrated perspective underscores the importance of developing and nurturing these personal attributes to successfully navigate the complexities of married student life (Augustine et al., 2018; Finkel, 2019).

Prioritization and Focus

The central theme of Prioritization and Focus highlights married students' strategic approach to managing their academic and marital responsibilities effectively. Prioritizing tasks and maintaining focus helps reduce role conflict by addressing the most critical and time-sensitive activities, minimizing stress, and enhancing productivity (Thorpe & Kuperberg, 2021). Prioritization within the family unit promotes clear communication and mutual understanding, enabling spouses to support each other's goals and responsibilities efficiently (Rindfuss & VandenHeuvel, 2019). This focused approach allows married students to allocate their time and energy where most needed, fostering a balance that enhances both their academic success and marital satisfaction (Freedman, 2019). Concentrating on critical priorities, these students can navigate their complex roles with greater clarity and purpose, ensuring that both domains are addressed (Finkel, 2019).

Struggles Faced by Married Students in Pursuit of their Degree

Figure 2 presents the thematic chart overview of married students' struggles in pursuing their degree. Three (3) significant themes were generated: relationship struggles, personal struggles, and balancing responsibilities.

Figure 2. Overview of the thematic chart on the struggles faced by married students in pursuit of their degree

Frame 2 displays the qualitative themes of the struggles faced by the married students in the pursuit of their degree. Moreover, Frame 2 presents sample verbatim responses in English or the language used (Cebuano) with a translation in English to support the themes and sub-themes.

Frame 2. Summary of the qualitative themes of the struggles faced by married students in the pursuit of their degree

Theme	Sub-theme	Sample Statement
Relationship Struggles	Lovers Quarrel	“Mag away sa paris” (Arguing with my partner)
	Family Problem	“Struggles nga na experience is naa gyud sa family” (Family life inevitably involves struggles)
Personal Struggles	Distraction	“Maka affect gyud siya usahay sa akong pag tuon” (Sometimes it really affects my studies)
	Discouragement	“Ma discourage ko makatagbo ko og dili maayo” (Encountering setbacks discourages me)
	Stress	“having stress”
	Sleep Deprivation	“I always end up not having a good and enough sleep”
Balancing Responsibilities	Academic Struggles	“Midterm - Struggle gyud” (Midterms is really a struggle)
	Financial Struggles	“Paying my tuition, books and other fees can be a financial burden”
	Family Concerns	“I am the eldest so naka center sa akoa ang ang pag human og ang pag tabang sa ilaha” (As the eldest, I'm the go-to for both finishing my studies and helping out)
	Juggling Roles	“Kinahanglan nako gampanan akong pagka studyante - kinahanglan pud nako nga dili mabiyaan and role as a mother” (Balancing my student and motherly duties is a must)
	Schedule Management	“Balancing my study and responsibilities can be a challenge”

Relationship Struggles

The central theme of Relationship Struggles reveals the significant challenges married students face in maintaining harmonious relationships while juggling academic responsibilities. Stress from academic demands can exacerbate conflicts and lead to the sub-themes of Lovers Quarrel and Family Problem. These struggles often stem from the limited time and emotional resources available to manage both roles effectively, leading to increased tension and misunderstandings (Brannen & Collard, 2023). Unresolved conflicts and family problems can disrupt the family system's equilibrium, creating a negative feedback loop that affects academic performance and marital satisfaction (Cleavelly, 2018). Addressing these struggles requires open communication, mutual support, and effective conflict resolution strategies within the family unit to ensure that academic and marital responsibilities are managed to minimize conflict and promote overall well-being (Finkel, 2019; Wallerstein, 2019).

Personal Struggles

The sub-themes of Distraction and Discouragement reflects the psychological barriers married students face as they balance academic and marital responsibilities. Distractions from familial obligations and household duties can impede academic focus, discouraging and reducing academic performance (Beard, 2018). If not managed well, these distractions can lead to a lack of support and understanding within the family unit, further intensifying feelings of discouragement (Cambri, 2021). The compounded effect of being unable to concentrate fully on academic tasks while feeling emotionally unsupported can lead to a negative spiral, impacting academic success and marital harmony (Freedman, 2019). The sub-themes of Stress and Sleep Deprivation highlights the physiological and emotional toll on married students who strive to meet the demands of academia and family life. The stress from balancing these dual roles can lead to sleep deprivation, adversely affecting cognitive function and overall well-being (Pepin et al., 2018). High stress levels and lack

of sleep can disrupt family dynamics, leading to increased irritability and reduced capacity for effective communication and support (Zuhara et al., 2017). This cycle of stress and sleep deprivation not only hampers academic performance but also strains marital relationships, creating a pervasive sense of overwhelm (Kordzanganeh et al., 2021).

The sub-themes of Academic Struggle and Financial Struggle underscores the dual pressures married students face in pursuing education while managing household finances. Financial stress can exacerbate academic difficulties, as money worries detract from the focus and energy needed for studies (Zuhara et al., 2017; Horne et al., 2018). Financial strain can lead to conflicts within the family system, as limited resources must be carefully allocated and managed (Arum et al., 2018). These academic and financial struggles are interlinked, amplifying the other and creating a significant barrier to academic success and marital stability (Kordzanganeh et al., 2021).

The overarching central theme of Personal Struggles emerges as a critical factor in the experiences of married students in academia. Personal struggles are multifaceted, encompassing psychological, physiological, and financial dimensions that collectively impact academic and marital domains (Zuhara et al., 2017). Distractions and discouragement undermine academic focus, stress and sleep deprivation impair cognitive and emotional well-being, and financial and academic struggles create a vicious cycle of pressure and conflict (Beard, 2018; Horne et al., 2018; Cambri, 2021). Addressing these personal struggles requires holistic strategies that consider the interconnected nature of these challenges, fostering resilience and support within the academic and family systems to enhance overall well-being and success (Freedman, 2019).

Balancing Responsibilities

The sub-theme of Family Concern highlights the dual emotional and practical challenges married students face regarding their families' well-being while pursuing academic goals. Concerns about family responsibilities, such as childcare, household management, and emotional support, can significantly detract from academic focus, leading to increased stress and potential conflict (Cleavelly, 2018; Kordzanganeh et al., 2021). A student's academic demands can strain family dynamics, requiring adaptation and support from all family members (Brannen & Collard, 2023). The constant worry about meeting family needs while fulfilling academic responsibilities creates a persistent tension that can affect academic performance and family harmony (Mannino et al., 2019), necessitating effective communication and shared responsibility within the family unit (Beyramijam et al., 2020).

The sub-themes of Juggling Roles and Schedule Management reflects the complex task of balancing multiple roles and managing time effectively, a common challenge for married students. Switching roles—student, spouse, and often parent—can lead to significant role strain and time conflicts, affecting academic and personal life (Abbaspour et al., 2020). Collaborative schedule management within the family is essential to meet each member's needs (Mishra, 2020). Effective juggling of roles and meticulous schedule management are crucial strategies that help married students allocate time efficiently, reducing conflicts and promoting a more balanced and fulfilling life (Kordzanganeh et al., 2021; Zaiceva, 2023). The overarching central theme of Balancing Responsibilities emerges as a dominant aspect of married students' academic experiences. Successfully balancing responsibilities involves addressing emotional concerns, managing multiple roles, and efficiently organizing schedules (Beatson et al., 2021). Family concerns demand emotional and practical support; juggling roles requires flexibility and adaptability, and schedule management necessitates strategic planning (Zuhara et al., 2017; Mishra, 2020). These elements underscore the need for an integrated approach where effective communication, mutual support, and collaborative planning within the family unit are essential (Finkel, 2019). This holistic balance enables married students to meet academic goals while maintaining healthy and supportive family relationships (Freedman, 2019).

Coping Strategies of Married Students for their Challenges in their Academic and Married Life

Figure 3 presents the overview of the thematic chart on married students' coping strategies for their academic and married life challenges. Two (2) significant themes were generated: personal development and learning and interpersonal relationships and support.

Figure 3. Overview of the thematic chart on the coping strategies of married students for their challenges in their academic and married life

Frame 3 displays the qualitative themes of the coping strategies of the married students for their challenges in their academic and married life. Moreover, Frame 3 presents sample verbatim responses in English or the language used (Cebuano) with a translation in English to support the themes and sub-themes.

Frame 3. Summary of the qualitative themes of the coping strategies of married students for their challenges in their academic and married life

Theme	Sub-theme	Sample Statement
Personal Development and Learning	Advance Study	“Advance ko usahay og basa kung naa koy vacant time” (I take advantage of my free time to read ahead)
	Hard Work	“Pag pursigi” (Persevere)
	Encouragement	“Dako kay tabang ang mga tao sa akong palibot” (I receive immense support from the people around me)
	Optimism	“Always think positive”
	Positive Mindset	“Naa kay strength mubakod sa adlaw-adlaw sag kapoy na kaayo” (I have the strength to persevere through the daily grind, even when I'm exhausted)
Interpersonal Relationship and Support	Prayer	“Prayer is always my weapon”
	Respect your Partner	“Always respect your partner”
	Family Support	“They are my support system”

Personal Development and Learning

The sub-themes of Advance Study and Hard Work highlight married students' dedication and proactive approach to managing their academic responsibilities effectively. Engaging in advanced study and exhibiting hard work are essential strategies to mitigate role conflicts (Beatson et al., 2021), allowing students to stay ahead of their coursework and reduce last-minute stress (Zuhara et al., 2017; Alvarez Sainz et al., 2019). Such diligence benefits the individual and positively influences the family dynamic by modeling discipline and commitment (Clark, 2019). This proactive stance in academics fosters a sense of achievement and stability, which can enhance academic success and family support structures (Mishra, 2020; Tus, 2021).

The sub-themes of Encouragement, Optimism, Positive Mindset, and Prayer underscore the importance of emotional and spiritual support in the lives of married students. These elements help buffer the stress of juggling academic and marital responsibilities by fostering resilience and emotional well-being (Sirgy & Lee, 2018). Encouragement and optimism within the family system enhance mutual support and communication, creating a positive environment conducive to managing dual roles (Kazim & Rafique, 2021). Prayer and a positive mindset serve as additional coping mechanisms, providing married students with a sense of purpose, hope, and inner strength to navigate their challenges effectively (Homaei & Dasht Bozorgi, 2018; Regnerus, 2020).

The overarching central theme of Personal Development and Learning emerges as a crucial aspect of married students' academic experiences. Personal development involves academic diligence, emotional resilience, and spiritual well-being (Beatson et al., 2021). Advance study and hard work reflect a commitment to academic excellence, while encouragement, optimism, a positive mindset, and prayer contribute to emotional and spiritual growth (Sirgy & Lee, 2018; Alvarez Sainz et al., 2019). These elements collectively enhance married students' capacity to manage their dual roles, fostering a balanced and enriched life where academic achievements and personal well-being are mutually reinforced through strategic effort and supportive relationships (Nicklin et al., 2019).

Interpersonal Relationship and Support

The central theme of Interpersonal Relationships and Support underscores the vital role that strong interpersonal dynamics and a robust support system play in the lives of married students balancing academic and marital responsibilities. The theme reveals that mutual respect and family support are essential in mitigating the stress and conflict inherent in managing dual roles (Finkel, 2019). Respecting one's partner fosters an environment of understanding and cooperation, reducing interpersonal tensions and facilitating better conflict resolution (Wallerstein, 2019). A supportive family unit, characterized by shared responsibilities and emotional encouragement, enhances the resilience and well-being of married students (Mishra, 2020). This support network provides practical assistance and bolsters emotional and psychological fortitude, enabling students to navigate their academic and marital commitments more effectively (Abbaspour et al., 2020). The relationship between respect and family support highlights how solid interpersonal relationships and a cohesive support system can significantly enrich academic achievements and marital satisfaction, promoting a balanced and fulfilling

life (Beatson et al., 2021).

Conclusions

The study comprehensively explores the challenges and strategies married students employ to balance their academic and marital responsibilities. By leveraging in-depth interviews and thematic analysis, the research reveals key themes that encapsulate the multifaceted experiences of these students. A central theme that emerged is the critical importance of time management and efficiency. Married students often experience significant stress due to competing demands on their time, leading to potential conflicts between their academic and marital roles. However, effective time management strategies, such as collaborative planning and prioritization, help mitigate these conflicts. These strategies enhance communication and mutual support within the marital relationship, fostering a more harmonious household and improving academic performance and marital satisfaction.

Another significant theme is the impact of attitude and mindset on managing dual roles. Optimism and a positive outlook are crucial in buffering the stress of juggling academic and marital responsibilities. A realistic and accepting attitude towards the inevitable trade-offs between academic pursuits and marital duties further aids in reducing internal conflict and fostering a sense of control and accountability. These attitudes promote mutual support, effective communication, and a balanced approach to managing responsibilities enriching academic and family life. Personal attributes such as dedication, motivation, discernment, and pragmatism are pivotal in navigating the complexities of married student life. Dedication and motivation drive students to succeed academically while managing marital responsibilities fostering a supportive environment within the family. Discernment helps make informed decisions about time and energy allocation, while pragmatism ensures realistic and attainable goals are set, reducing potential conflicts. Balancing these personal attributes is essential for maintaining an equilibrium between academic and marital commitments.

The study also highlights the significant relationship struggles that married students face. Stress from academic demands can exacerbate conflicts, leading to issues such as lovers' quarrels and family problems. These struggles often result from limited time and emotional resources, creating a negative feedback loop affecting academic performance and marital satisfaction. Addressing these struggles requires open communication, mutual support, and effective conflict-resolution strategies within the family unit. Married students face various psychological and physiological struggles, including distractions, discouragement, stress, and sleep deprivation. These challenges impede academic focus and strain marital relationships. Financial struggles further exacerbate academic difficulties, detracting from the focus needed for studies. Coping mechanisms such as time management, a positive mindset, and effective prioritization are crucial for mitigating these challenges and fostering resilience.

In conclusion, the study underscores the intricate dynamics and significant challenges married students face in balancing academic and marital responsibilities. Effective time management, a positive attitude, and essential personal attributes are critical in navigating these dual roles. Addressing relationship struggles through open communication and mutual support is vital for maintaining harmony and ensuring academic success. The findings highlight the need for tailored support systems within academic institutions to help married students manage their responsibilities effectively, promoting their overall well-being and academic achievement. This integrated perspective emphasizes the importance of viewing married student life through the lens of both academic and family systems, fostering a balanced and enriching experience in both domains.

Based on the findings from the study, several key recommendations have been identified to enhance support for married students and guide further research. Institutions could dedicate counseling services to address academic and marital issues, providing emotional and psychological support through conflict resolution strategies, stress management techniques, and time management workshops. Moreover, enhancing communication and support networks is also crucial. Creating peer support groups for married students can foster community and provide a platform for sharing experiences and strategies.

Further research is needed to provide deeper insights into the experiences of married students. Longitudinal studies tracking these students over time can highlight the long-term effects on academic performance and marital satisfaction. Additionally, including a diverse range of married students in research, such as those from different cultural backgrounds, socioeconomic statuses, and fields of study, will offer a more comprehensive understanding of their unique challenges.

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